

Cotton Textile Industry in 16th and 17th Century India: An analysis

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In India, the 17th century was an era of stabilization. The industrial organization of the country during this period was sound, and articles of merchandise were made in such abundance that the country was as a whole not only self-sufficient but had a huge surplus which was exported to different regions of the world. A comparative study of the contemporary industrial conditions in India and Europe tends to create the impression that in this respect India was more advanced than the European countries. Urban handicrafts of high quality in textiles, and other luxury products of artistic taste were flourishing under the patronage of the royalty and nobility. Foreign merchants flocked to India and Indian products enjoyed a worldwide reputation. A leading factor in moulding the industrial organization of the country, which consisted mainly of handicrafts in this period, was the impact of the different European nations which had established trade with India. The English East India Company was launched on its fateful career of commercial enterprise here along with the Dutch, French and Portuguese merchants during the seventeenth century. The textile handicrafts which included the manufacture of cotton, silken and woollen cloths and other allied stuffs of different varieties, were the chief industry which was spread all over India. All capital towns, like Agra, Delhi, Lahore, Multan, Thatta, Ahmadabad, Baroch, Surat, Cambay, Burhanpur, Patna and Dacca were the chief centres for the textile industry. In addition to major towns, other centres were also famous for the textile industry. Cotton fabrics of all kinds were manufactured in Sarhind, Samana, Nasarpur, Sehwan, Sironj, Nosari, Shahzadpur and Sonargaon. The manufacture of silk cloth was also widespread in many urban centres. Of these the most famous were Benaras, Murshidabad, Kasimbazar, Srinagar, Sialkot and Malda.

The country's leading manufacture, cotton textiles, was produced probably in every part of the country both for local consumption and distant markets. The bewildering variety of cotton fabrics mentioned in the contemporary sources - 150 names occur in the first ten years of the English factory records - can be divided into a number of overlapping categories according to the criteria of classification used. They were produced as piece-goods or ready-made clothing (which involved little tailoring); calico, a stout cloth, or muslin (which was thinner); plain (i.e. unbleached), bleached and dyed or patterned. Calico was the most important of the cotton goods manufactured in India. It was produced everywhere in India, that of Calicut being the most famous. Calicoes are plain cotton cloth (bleached, unbleached, or dyed in various colours- the most important being indigo) made in pieces of twelve to fifteen yards long by less than three-fourths of a yard broad and in Gujarat were called Dutties (Dhoties or loin-cloth) or baftas (calico of finer texture than Dutties). Baftas were worn by women, while men put on Dutties. Longcloth was the name given to Calico made on the Coast. The Longcloth of the Coromandel coast was famous, though long pieces called Guzzes (from Gaz meaning a yard) were also manufactured in Northern India. Different kinds of calico were made in India and the uncoloured pieces were sent either to Ahmadabad or Agra (indigo centres) to be dyed. Seinianoes was the name given to calico manufactured in Semiana in Northern India. The Portuguese gave the name of Pintados to calico which had patterns in colour. Striped calico was called Necanies, while pieces of plain calico were called Percalles. The Calicos were known by the following names in different parts of India: Amberteas (Bihar), Broad Baftas (Gujrat), Narrow Baftas (Gujrat), Dariyabads (manufactured at Dariyabad which lies midway between

Lucknow and Fayzabad), Salempore (East coast), Moorees (East coast), Kerriabauds (Khairabad near Lucknow), Mercoolis (Western Oudh).

The other type of cotton cloth of better quality was muslins. They were thinner in texture and lighter in weight. They were suitable for use in hot countries; hence they were exported to Persia, Arabia and Egypt. In Bengal Sonargaon was the most important on account of the special quality possessed by its tank water which could turn the cloth extremely white. The Portuguese extended the trade to Turkey, Persia and North-West Africa where the muslins were used for turbans. Varthema mentions about Tanda in Bengal that this place abounds more in grain, flesh of every kind, in great quantity of sugar, also of ginger, and of great abundance of cotton, than any country in the world and here there are the richest merchants I ever met with. Fifty ships are laden every year in this place with cotton and silk stuffs that is to say, Bairam, Namone, Lizati, Ciantar, Doazar, and Sinabaff.

Dress and fancy goods, including pintados, chintzes, handkerchiefs, short dyed pieces of calico, goods woven with patterns, and cloths with an intermixture of silk were demanded in the foreign markets. Up to 1660, there was a very weak demand for muslins or printed goods in Western Europe. Calico was, however, much in demand. Ralph Fitch speaking of Sinnergan (Sonargaon, the capital of Eastern Bengal, 1351-1608, situated fifteen miles east of Dacca) says, "Sinnergan is a town six leagues from Serrepore, where there is the best and finest cloth made of cotton that is in all India." Chintzes or painted cotton cloths were made in Golconda particularly in the neighbourhood of Masulipatam and Sironj.

Various cotton cloths mentioned by Abul Fazl in Ain-i-Akbari were Chautar in Haweli (Saharanpur), Siri saf and Bhiraun in Dharangaon (Khandesh), Gangajal in Ghoraghat (Bengal), Mihrkul in Allahabad. According to Jadunath Sarkar cotton fabrics could be classified into five categories- (i) white ordinary (ii) coloured ordinary, both plain in texture and known in England as calicoes, (iii) flowered (iv) chintz or printed cloth, and (v) muslin. Course white cotton cloths were exported from Lower Sind, Bengal and Orissa and other places on the east coast of India to many countries of Southern Asia and the Indian Archipelago, and in small quantities to Japan. Towards the end of the 17th century a market was found for them in England also. As for cotton cloths worked in gold and silver, Banaras and Ahmadabad were the chief centres of their manufactures and from those places they were exported to all parts of the world.

Tavernier tells a lot of things about cotton cloth. He says, "The chiles (chintz) or painted cotton cloths which are called calmendar that is to say, made with a brush, are made in the Kingdom of Golconda, and especially in the neighbourhood of Masulipatam. The chites (chintz) which are made in the Empire of the Great Mogul are printed, and are of different degrees of beauty, both on account of the printing and the fineness of the cotton cloth. Those made at Lahore are the coarsest of all, and consequently the cheapest. They are sold by corges, a corge consisting of 20 pieces, and costing from 16 to 30 rupees. The chites (chintz) which are made at Sironj are sold at from 20 to 60 rupees the corge or thereabouts." The chites(chintz) of bright colours are made at Burhanpur. The baftas or cotton cloths to be dyed red, blue, or black, are taken uncoloured to Agra and Ahmadabad, because these two towns are near the places where the Indigo is made, which is used in dyeing. According to Bernier there was no other country where so great variety is found. In Bengal he was amazed at the vast quantity of cotton cloths, of every sort, fine and coarse, white and coloured, which the Hollanders alone export to different places, especially to Japan and Europe. The English, the Portuguese, and the native merchants deal also in these articles to a considerable extent. White cotton cloths come partly from Agra and the vicinity of Lahore, partly from Bengal, and some from Baroda, Broach, Navasari and other places. The cotton cloths which come from Agra, Lahore, and Bengal are sold by corges, and they cost from 16 up to 300 or 400 rupees and more, according as the merchant directs them to be made. Gujarat was noted in the time of Akbar for the excellence of its cotton goods. Abul fazl writes of 'Stuffs worked with gold threads of the Kinds of Chirah,

fotah (a partly coloured cloth used for turbans), Jamawar (a kind of flowered woollen stuff well-known as khara), Khara, velvets and brocades were skilfully manufactured there.’

The capital city of Delhi specialised in the production of chintz and quilts. Its chintzes are reported to have been inferior only to those of Masulipatam. Again, it was the Armenian and Persian merchants who were chiefly interested in this commodity. The fabrics of Panipat were of the same measurement as those of Samana and used to be sent to Sirhind and Lahore for the benefit of the said merchants. In Oudh, Lucknow was one of the principal centres of cotton fabrics from the early 17th century and W. Finch had found great traffic in ‘linen’ here. Pelsaert noted the production of coarse cotton stuffs in Oudh. English factors were greatly interested in Lucknow’s ‘mercools’ and ‘daryabadis’ though not in its guzzes. Daryabadis and khairabadis so much in demand among the European traders were principally produced in Daryabad (Barabanki District) and Khairabad (Sitapur District) and that is how these stuffs acquired their names. Benaras also fabricated shashes (turban- clothes) for the Moores. The volume of the local output of cotton goods certainly impressed Ralph Fitch while he was at Benaras. Similarly Pelsaert recorded the manufacture here of several varieties such as girdles, turbans, saris and gangajal. With the advent of European traders at the beginning of the 17th century the industry seems to have been greatly stimulated. Amertees, a coarse kind of stuff was largely woven in Lakhawar (south of Patna). Pelsaert also corroborates the production of coarse muslin (cassa) at Patna. Bazwara, a district of Hoshiarpur in the Punjab, manufactured different kinds of cotton goods; Sirisaf, Adhars, Doriah, panchtoliah, jhonah, white cherah, fotah of gold embroidery and other kinds of cloth. Broach was famous for alchab cloth.

The most important of the urban industries were cotton and silk-weaving. Throughout the seventeenth century Aurangabad, for instance, was famous for white cotton cloth and silk-stuff, and Burhanpur for fine white and printed cloth, which was exported in quantities by Persian and Armenian merchants to Persia, Arabia and Turkey. Especially the cities of the Qutbshahi kingdom produced a large quantity of printed cloth which was claimed to be the best to be found in India. They also manufactured all sorts of calicoes which were as cheap and plentiful as in any other part of India, but different in texture and pattern from those of other regions. Tavernier tells about Sironj that this is a large town, of which the majority of the inhabitants are Banian merchants and artisans, who have dwelt there from father to son, which is the reason why it contains some houses of stone and brick. There is a large trade there in all kinds of coloured calicoes, which they call chites, with which all the common people of Persia and Turkey are clad, and which are used in several other countries for bedcovers and tablecloths. On the western coast, Chaul was famous for fine linens and silk cloth till about 1670, and Bhivandi also excelled in the weaving industry.

The cotton textiles industry, by virtue of its general diffusion and the extent of its production, came to exercise a direct impact on the economy of our entire region, a fact which was further accentuated by its very essential character, as clothing constitutes the second basic need of mankind. In the tropical climates cotton fabrics are a necessity and silken and woollen stuffs a luxury - a factor which ensured a steady, and with the multiplication of the population, a growing demand for cotton fabrics both within the country and abroad. In practice, it implied that these were the principal sources of earning foreign exchange or constituted the medium for increasing the aggregate wealth of the region under review. All cloth fabricated in excess of local requirements was so much foreign money assured. Some town or city took to cotton industry as one of the principal means for multiplying its productive resources. The capital cities or even administrative centres such as Lucknow and Farrukhabad provide evidence of the tendency. As a matter of fact, in some cases the towns were entirely dependent upon this industry, the rise and fall of the town corresponding with the growth and decline of the industry. Samana, Khairabad and Daryabad may be cited as examples. In others, like Benaras or Patna, on the other hand, it occupied a complementary position to their commercial traffic. The relationship between the two -cotton textiles production and commerce is plain enough.

The cotton textile industry was growing steadily during the reign of Emperor Akbar, its real boom begins with the turn of the 17th century. Four factors seem to have been most important in determining, its trend in this direction; first, continual peace and stability stretching over a long period; secondly, extension of cultivation of cotton, crops; thirdly, freedom of commercial intercourse, including liberal facilities accorded to the foreign traders without prejudicing the rights of the local merchants; and finally, relative safety and conveniences of the main commercial highways. Thus, throughout the 17th century, town after town was being added to the existing centres of piece-goods production.

All the things of the world used to change from time to time, in the same way, the cotton textile industry also changed later. In the era of Akbar's successors after 16th century, the society was started to earn a big income by making cotton to make cotton garments and in the greed of profit, the upper class women of the society even in some places in the house of Brahmins, the making of yarn was started.

The cotton textile industry was booming during the reign of Emperor Akbar, whose real explosion began in the early 17th century. Four factors seem to be very important in determining, its tendency to this approach; first, lasting peace and stability; second, the expansion of cotton cultivation crops; thirdly, the freedom to participate in trade, including free institutions provided to foreign traders without prejudice to the rights of local merchants; and finally, the safety associated with the use of commercial highways. Thus, throughout the 17th century, various cities were added to existing production facilities.

Thus we see that in the Mughal Indian society, the cotton textile industry had maintained a unique status like the ancient Indian industry and this cotton textile was based solely on its agriculture, for which raw materials were produced indigenously. The quality of cotton textiles manufactured in the country can be studied by the fact that in some countries there was a primary demand for Indian cotton textiles. In the records of Ain-i-Akbari and European companies, many names of varieties of cotton cloth are found which shows their high level of expertise. The country's largest farming people had made a living through agriculture as well as cotton textile industry. From 16th century to 17th century cotton textile industry remained the largest industry in India.

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